

Conference Abstract

Towards an eLTER and ICOS scientific dialogue and cooperation - a contribution from the basis

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Abstract

The sites connecting in eLTER combine a network that encompasses very diverse landscapes. Our study area, the AgroScapeLab Quillow (LTER Site DE-07-UM, Germany), is characterised by agriculture. In contrast to near-natural forms, such as forests and peatlands, arable farming has a high frequency of external interventions. Moreover, in addition to the passive monitoring also experimental research with manipulative interventions is executed.

The range of landscape components and processes analysed in the AgroScapeLab Quillow is therefore very broad, with many direct and indirect links to issues relating to GHG. The long-term observations of various environmental variables and agricultural management practices are hereby designed to decipher the systemic relationships. For example, the investigations focusing on anthropogenically controlled primary production are connected to the biomass production in -and the N₂O and CH₄ emissions from- small natural ponds, affected by eutrophication after lateral transport in the groundwater.

In contrast, the ICOS program focusses on accurate determination of GHG exchange between soil or water bodies and atmosphere at a local scale within a limited footprint and the effects of local drivers therein. Nevertheless, we see great potential for synergies between the ICOS and the eLTER approach. But there are some issues that need to be addressed. In particular, our contribution will take a position in regards to

1. What common goals could be achieved?

2. What does this mean for the contributing sites:

- with regard to necessary modifications and additions to the observations and the experimental design?
- with respect to the compatibility of the data (quality, resolution)?

Presenting author

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Presented at

POSTER

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.